

MIGRATIONS OF DAKH TRIBES IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Abstract: This article analyzes the causes, directions and results of migrations of the Dakh tribes, one of the ancient nomads of Central Asia, based on archaeological and written sources. Also, information on the causes and results of changes in the ancient deltas of the Syrdarya River were analyzed.

Keywords: Dakhs, migrations, Syrdarya, Massagets, Herodotus, Sarmatians, Kuvandarya, Inkardarya, Zhanadarya, Tasmolin and Jetiasar culture.

The large migration of the Dakhs of the III-II centuries BC, the starting point of which was the lower reaches of the Syrdarya, was of great importance in the ethnogenesis and cultural genesis of Central Asia. In written sources of various origins, very brief, but numerous messages have been preserved about this event. The advancement of the Dakhs is well traced by archaeological sources.

The studies of the Khorezm archaeological and ethnographic expedition established that after the defeat of Cyrus by the army of nomadic tribes and peoples led by the Massagets, according to Herodotus, by the middle of the first millennium BC, Chirikrabort and Jetiasar archaeological cultures were formed on the basis of the ancient delta channels of the Syrdarya. However, after two centuries of successful development, the Chirikrabort culture is in crisis due to the dynamics of the tectonic plates of the Turan lowland, because of which serious changes in the landscape occur, which leads to a constant hypsometric increase in the slope of the entire Eastern Aral Sea region from south to north. This, in turn, leads to the fact that less and less water from the middle riverbed enters the southern channels of the ancient Syrdarya delta. It ends with the fact that in the third century BC, the river in its lower reaches breaks into a new northern channel, passing by Atrou (Kazalinsk) and flows

into the Aral Sea from the northeast, which leads to the final drainage of the territory of the Chirikrabort culture. By B.I. Vaynberg, considers this culture to belong to those mentioned in written sources of the 4th-2nd centuries BC. B.I.Vaynberg describes features of the culture of the Dakhs in a number of publications. The exodus of the dakhs from their homeland in the lower reaches of the Syrdarya occurred gradually as the crisis grew [1, pp. 3-5; 2, p. 359].

In the Greek historical tradition, dakhs are first mentioned in the "History" of Herodotus. Dakhs are also mentioned in the Fravardin-Yasht of the Avesta along with arya, tura, sairima and saina [4, p. 207]. The fact that the Dakhs and Sarimas are mentioned in the same list, whether the latter are compared with Savromatians or Sarmatians, indicates that they were different peoples. Later in the 4th century BC, the Dakhs are mentioned as members of the first Achaemenid troops, and then Alexander. Genetically, the Dakhs may have been related to the Savromatians and Sarmatians of the south of the Urals. The Ural River - the medieval Yayik was named by Ptolemy - Daik, that is, it is associated with the ethnonym Dakhs or Dayes. In the 4th-2nd centuries BC, Dakhs are mentioned south of the Amu Darya in Khorezm, on Uzboy and Atrek, as well as in the Zarafshan basin. According to the entire archaeological complex, they were genetically related to the Prokhorov culture of the Southern Urals [3, pp. 11-24].

At the same time, the pairs included in the association of Dakhs, led by Arsaces and Tiridates, captured Parthia. Under Mithridates the Great, the rulers of Parthia expand their borders to Mesopotamia in the southwest and push the Kushans in the east, in the north they own lands up to Turiva - Tarab and Kazbion - Kaspi in the south - from the outskirts of Sogd. Finally, the Dakhs leave their homeland at the turn of the 3rd-2nd centuries BC, when, as a result of another tectonic uplift, the Syrdarya left along a new, or modern northern channel and began to flow into the Aral Sea from the northeast. There are no settlements along this new lower part of the river before the 2nd century BC. The final drying up of the lower reaches of the

ancient delta channels of the Kuvandarya, Inkardarya and Zhanadarya took place. [4, pp. 25-31]

The fortified settlements of the Jetiasar culture, located in the upper part of the Syrdarya delta, closer to the modern riverbed, continued to settle down during the first half of the first millennium AD, and the further fate of the people of this culture is somewhat different.

The oldest among the monuments of the Chirikrabort culture is their first capital city, represented by the ruins of the settlement of Chirikrabort with the burial structures of the leaders of the 5th - 4th centuries BC. An oval defensive wall surrounds the city. The second in time is the ancient settlement of Babishmola. It was a fortress-type building, in the form of a monumental, square high castle, surrounded by a square defensive wall with a high impregnable tower at the entrance, which was functionally connected with the castle itself by a swing bridge. B.I. Weinberg dates this castle to the 4th century BC and believes that it was erected as the residence of the satrap after the inclusion of the Dahi lands into the empire as allies of the Achaemenids. However, the castle remained unfinished, as already in the 4th century BC. Khorezm, and with it the Dakhs, gained independence. At the same time, to the south in Khorezm, the largest settlement of Kalalikir turned out to be unfinished and uninhabited. The country of the Dakhs, through which the large and small channels of the Syrdarya delta flowed, was inhabited and cultivated, but in the process of the mentioned endogenous ecological catastrophe, it became depopulated.

Dahi, as already noted, and earlier, from the 5th-4th century BC, roamed and went on campaigns in Central Asia. This is evidenced by the numerous burial grounds of the side-chamber and catacomb types, studied along the middle reaches of the Syrdarya, Zarafshan, as well as in the Kyzylkum. [5, pp. 31-42]. All experts are practically unanimous in their opinion about the common origin and unity of the material culture of the Dakhs and Sarmatians. Dakhs left in the second century BC. the lower reaches of the Syrdarya, for all their commonality with the Scythian-

Sarmatian world of the early nomads, already had a two-hundred-year experience of a settled agricultural and pastoral and, moreover, urbanized culture. The last and final exodus of the Dakhs to the south and east at the turn of the 3rd-2nd centuries BC served as an impetus for a wave of other nomadic peoples, which swept away in the 2nd century BC. The last Greek rulers - the heirs of Alexander and gave rise to new dynasties of autochthonous origin. As noted, part of them invades Parthia, the other part, passing through Sogd and Bactria and passing through the Hindu Kush, occupies the lands to the middle reaches of the Indus, where in the first centuries BC. The so-called Indo-Scythian or Indo-Parthian kingdoms are known. They mint their own silver coin, by which the names of such rulers as Vonon, Maues, Azes are known.

But the Dakhs, not only in the face of their warlike clans prone to nomadism, occupy the vast territories of the fragmented heirs of the empire, but over time, the last wave of them completely leaves their homeland mastered by their ancestors and populates the lands along the middle course of the Syrdarya. The last act of this ecological drama takes place at the end of the 3rd-2nd centuries BC. When, as a result of the breakthrough of the channel of the Syrdarya to the north-west, the irrigated lands of the Dakhs - carriers of the Chirikrabat culture, as a result of drying, became completely unsuitable for agriculture. This led to the exodus from the homeland of those Dakh communities that had long been leading a sedentary lifestyle based on an integrated cattle-breeding and agricultural economy. They migrate up along the Syrdarya, along the right bank of the river, which was partially irrigated by small rivulets that ran down to the bed of the Syrdarya from the southern slopes of the Karatau ridge - the northern watershed of the Syrdarya basin. In the process of migration, they begin to develop lands suitable for agriculture. Later, some of them go further to Yettisuv, as evidenced by the ceramic complexes of these areas of the first half of the 1st millennium BC. Along the middle course of the river in the II century. BC. Two new ethno-cultural communities are formed, represented by the Otrar-Karatau and Kovinchi archaeological cultures. These cultures have

been studied for a long time and to a sufficient extent. The groups of Dakhs who settled here spread the skills of their original early city culture to the right bank of the Syrdarya. The foundations of such cities and towns as Sygnak, Sauran, Yasi (Turkestan), Otrar, Chimkent, Tashkent, Taraz, and a number of fortified settlements located in a dotted line between the listed cities appear in the II - I centuries BC. Long-term excavations carried out in Tashkent, Chimkent and Taraz confirmed two thousand years, and their older age.

This phenomenon is fundamentally different from the previous migration of nomadic Dakhs, who implement the traditional model of nomadic migration, when they rally and, thanks to their mobility and military superiority, despite their small numbers, capture wealthy but defenseless areas in order to receive tribute. In this case, they act as occupiers, where the aristocracy of the Dakhs, in the role of new masters, moves into the urban centers of the occupied lands. [6, pp. 18-26]. However, in both cases, wherever they appeared, there are clear innovations in the signs of Dakh culture. This is manifested in urban planning and architecture, in funeral rites and weapons, in art and religious traditions. At the same time, the features of the appearance of the material culture of the Dakhs retain features inherent not only in the Prokhorov culture, but also in the Sarmatian culture in Eastern Europe. This is emphasized by all researchers of burial mounds in the Syrdarya valley, Zarafshan and the right bank of the Amu Darya [7; 8].

We believe that the formation of the Chirikrabad and Prokhorovka cultures occurred not only synchronously, but also syngenetically, and the bearers of these two archaeological cultures constituted the association of the Dakhs. Then, from the 3rd century BC, when the oasis of the Dakhs in the delta of the Syrdarya began to dry up, all the Dakhs began to move, one of the consequences of which was the penetration of some of them into the territory of the Savromats. After the aliens merged with the latter, they began to be called Sarmatians.

In material culture, the influence of the Dakhs on the urban planning of Sogd was clearly manifested in the Nakhshab in the lower reaches of the Kashkadarya.

Here, in the second century BC, 10 km south of the existing capital city, a new grandiose fortified city of the fortress type Kalai Zakhaki Moron - the Fortress of the Serpent Zakhak, was built on the site of Yerkurgan. Dakhs of the Aral Sea in the lower reaches of the Syrdarya in exaggeratedly enlarged sizes and with three times as many walls. The castle itself and the second row of walls of Kalai Zakhaki Moron have massive ledges on their southern face, corresponding to the gate keep of Babishmola. We can assume that it was this city - the fortress of the Dahas - that was the center of the sovereignty of the new masters of the country. The very name Zakhak or Dahak points to his connection with the ethnonym Dakh. Judging by the grandiose scale of Kalai Zakhaki Moron, the power of the rulers of the new residence of the Dakhs in Nakhshab extended far beyond the borders of Nakhshab proper and Sogd. There were no fortresses of this magnitude either in Sogd or in Bactria. At the same time, the former Hellenized capital of Nakhshab on the settlement of Yerkurgan is apparently assigned the role of a trade and craft center of the oasis. It is important to note that before the development of the territory of the settlement by the modern city of Karshi, the rural settlement Kat was located here, the old-timers remembered this in the second half of the 20th century. Kat is a traditional toponym for cities and fortifications in the Eastern Aral Sea region, including the name of the capital city and early medieval Khorezm, and this term is probably associated with the language of Dakhs.

A few iconographic material known from the painting and sculpture of the temples of Central Asia in the first centuries BC and AD, as well as plots of toreutics of the famous burials of Tillatepe I in BC in northern Afghanistan, testify to the spread of the cult of female deities of the Dakh tribes - the Sarmatian circle. The traditionally high position of women and mothers was certainly a legacy of earlier Savromatians, for whom Greek sources noted an exotic gynecocracy for them. The Savromats played their part in the formation of the culture of both the Sarmatians and the Idakhs. But in the statehood of the Dakhs, this was combined with the cult of ancestors - the founders of certain dynasties. Later, among the rulers of Parthia,

under the influence of the Hellenistic rulers, it is combined with the cult of the deified king - the founder of the dynasty, which was initiated by Alexander himself, who, after the capture of Egypt, which previously belonged to the Achaemenids, the priests of the temple of Amun declared the liberator and son of the sun god Ra.

The second major migration from the Syrdarya basin occurs in the 4th century BC. It was a migration of the distant descendants of the Dakhs - the people of Kovunchi and Otrar.

A number of researchers come to the conclusion that the impetus for the exodus and migration of nomads in Central Asia was given by extreme climatic changes in the 8th-7th centuries BC in the deserts and steppes of Central Asia, and possibly earlier. [9, p. 592; 10, pp. 170-172] At the same time, the culture of migrants from the East in Central Kazakhstan is superimposed on the autochthonous cultural traditions of the Dandybay and Begazy cultures. The same process also occurs with the late Andronovo and Srubnaya cultures of the western regions of Central Asia, which led in the 8th-7th centuries BC to the emergence of a number of local cultures of the Scythian type. All experts note that the ethno-cultural traditions of the migrants themselves were rather heterogeneous. Among these new local cultures, the Tasmolin cultural community stood out in its scale, stretching from the Balkhash region in the East to the Urals in the West.

In this matter, attention should also be paid to some features of the architectural monuments of the Dakhs and Massagets. Firstly, attention should be paid to the similarity of the composition of the plans of the fortress centers of the Dakhs in the lower reaches of the Syrdarya and the city-fortress of Kalai Zakhaki Moron, 10 kilometers from Erkugan. The planning principle is strictly centric, only in the first earlier case - con. IV in BC, a square wall surrounds the same square tower of the castle. In the second case, on Kalai Zahaki, Moron, gigantic in scale and high square fortification, surrounds three rows of square walls. The principle is the same, the idea of centrality goes back to the Median round Khakmadana surrounded by seven rows of concentric walls, as well as to the even more ancient round temple of Dashla

3 where the inner walls are round in plan, and outside are still surrounded by a fourth square wall. These prototypes of the sacred centers of the Bronze Age and the early Iron Age hint at the fact that the military and administrative centers of the Dakhs served at the same time as their cult shrines.

As for the Massagets, the Jetiasar culture, their round fortifications undoubtedly have an early city character and are distinguished by their spiral layout, the prototypes of which go far to the west into the archaic of the Bronze Age, as S.P. Tolstov pointed out in his time. But the hypertrophied thickness of the outer walls of not only settlements, but also temple structures seems to go back to the monumental mausoleums of Dandybai and Begazy, the walls of the cyclopean masonry of stone crypts of which are several meters thick [11, p. 74]. We see the reproduction of this tradition on the monumental western construction of the city temple of Yerkurgan IV - V centuries. This majestic building has been previously studied. It is square in plan and the outer facade of its walls has a pyramidal profile and the thickness of the walls at the base reaches 8 meters. At the same time, a majestic mausoleum was being built on the site of Yerkurgan in ancient Nakhshab in the southern part of the outer city. BC. The remains of the rulers of the city and the region of the 4th century BC were buried in the mausoleum. The burial was performed according to the Zoroastrian rite - cleaned bones in large ceramic pots. The skulls of the buried had a Hunnic ring deformation. Similar skulls elongated because of deformation are noted at this time in Khorezm and a number of other burials in Central Asia [12, fig. 63]. L.M. Levina notes the influence of the Huns on the Jetiasar culture from the 1st century BC. [13, p. 57]. Further, it is noted that in the 3rd-4th centuries, many settlements of the Jetiasar perished in the fire of the second wave of the invasion of the Huns of the 3rd-4th centuries. This is followed by a large migration of them to the North Caucasus and further to the west, as well as upstream along the Syrdarya. Let us add on our own behalf that at the same time a large group of Jetiasar also migrated to the southeast to the oasis of ancient Nakhshab.

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